

Blue Action WP5

Developing and Valuing Climate Services

Mark R Payne

National Institute for Aquatic
Resources, Denmark

Kathrin Keil

Institute For Advanced Sustainability
Studies, Germany

DTU Aqua

National Institute of Aquatic Resources

What is a climate service?

We attribute to the term a broad meaning, which covers the ***transformation of climate-related data*** — together with other relevant information — ***into customised products*** such as projections, forecasts, information, trends, economic analysis, assessments (including technology assessment), counselling on best practices, development and evaluation of solutions and any other service in relation to climate that may be of use for the society at large. As such, these services include data, information and knowledge that ***support adaptation, mitigation and disaster risk management*** (DRM)

- European Roadmap for Climate Services

"Climate data is not climate information"

- *Francisco Doblas-Reyes*

Climate models
& modellers

End-users &
stakeholders

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Climate

WP5 Objectives

Translate the skill of forecast models into products that are relevant to stakeholders

Demonstrate the value of these products to stakeholders and estimate their economic value

End-Users are Key

Five Case Studies Applying a Common(ish) Approach

Temperature Related Mortality (TRM) (Joan Ballester, IC3)

Develop forecast scheme for thermal stress and TRM for 160 administrative units across Europe

e.g. Excess Mortality due to
2003 Summer Heatwave

Both summer and winter
temperatures are important

Winter Tourism Industry in Lapland (Pamela Lesser, U. Lapland)

Seasonal forecasts of winter conditions to 1) allow for planning of activities & 2) compare with Alps to establish competitiveness of Lapland

Planning of snow-making and storage requirements

Planning of alternative activities

Polar Low Forecasts (Erik Kolstad, Uni Research)

Prediction of cold air outbreaks and polar low environments to incorporate into shipping risk assessment tools

Polar Low in Barents Sea

Safety risk map for August

Impacts of resource extraction on Russian Arctic

(Kathrin Keil, IASS Potsdam)

Collaboratively develop scenarios outlining possible impacts of climate change on stakeholders in the region

Climate Services for Fisheries (Mark Payne, DTU Aqua)

Develop forecasts for the distribution, productivity and timing of commercially important fish stocks

Applications in scientific monitoring of fish stocks

Planning and performance of commercial fisheries

A revolution in forecasting the ocean is taking place....

A revolution in three acts

Climate Model improvements

Observational Advances

Data assimilation

Seasonal-scale forecasting of the ocean is a reality

NMME Ensemble, SST Hindcast Correlation skill, 5 months lead

Decadal-scale forecasting of the ocean is a reality

MPI-ESM-LR Model, SST Hindcast Correlation skill, 2-5 years lead

Can we translate physical predictions into user-relevant climate services?

Examples of forecast products already in operation

Great Australian Bight Tuna Distribution Forecasts

Fortnight 1:
22 Feb – 7 Mar

Fortnight 2:
8 Mar – 21 Mar

Month 1:
March

Month 2:
April

SST

Habitat

SE Australia Long-line Fishery Area-Based Closures to protect Tuna

California Current "J-SCOPE" system forecasting Ecosystem

Upwelling

Chl-a

Sardine Habitat

Gulf of Maine Lobster – Timing of landings

Gulf of Maine Research Institute
Science. Education. Community.

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Gulf of Maine Lobster Forecasting

Project Overview

We are forecasting the timing of when the Maine lobster fishery will shift into its high-landings mode for the summer. Our goal is to provide 2-3 months advance notice of this uptick so that the lobster industry can prepare appropriately for the high-landings period.

2016 Forecast

April 13 Forecast

Extremely Early	Very Early	Early	Normal	Late	Very Late	Extremely Late
41%	56%	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%
6/12	6/19	6/26	7/3	7/10	7/17	7/24

2016 Final Forecast

Temperatures in Maine’s coastal waters have been warm throughout the beginning of 2016. The temperatures at 50-meters (164 ft) at four coastal NERACCOOS buoys in the Gulf of Maine remain approximately 1 degree Celsius (1.8 degrees Fahrenheit) warmer than normal. Across the region, sea surface temperatures have been running 0.5 – 1 degrees Celsius warmer than normal over the past week, with the Maine coast being at the cool end of the range. Based on the current buoy temperatures, our forecast predicts a 41% chance that the season will start three weeks earlier than normal, a 56% chance that it will start two weeks early, and only a 3% chance that it will begin one week early. We consider the normal high-landings period for Maine lobster to start between July 3 and 10.

Project Overview

GMRI Scientists:
[Andrew Pershing](#)
[Kathy Mills](#)

Research Theme:
Climate Adaptation

Project Status:
Ongoing

Related Research

[Climate Vulnerability and Adaptation Assessment](#)

[Gulf of Maine Lobster Forecasting](#)

[Impacts of Climate Change on Lobsters, Fish, and Economics](#)

[Finding Ocean Solutions](#)

[2015 Lobster Forecast](#)

[All Climate Adaptation Projects](#)

DTU Aqua Products in Development

Bluefin Tuna Potential Habitat

Significant skill to more than 10 years

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Bluefin Tuna Habitat Forecasts

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Predicted Mackerel Egg Counts for MEGS 2016

DTU Aqua Products in Development

Predictions for MEGS 2016

June (Period 6) Details

Suggests potential refinements to the design

DTU Aqua Products in Development

Blue Whiting Spawning Distribution

Expanded Distribution

Compacted Distribution

Blue whiting spawning distribution is related to conditions in the Rockall region – and is predictable!

Acknowledgements

Arctic Impact on Weather and Climate

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